

Surviving the Edge: Federated Learning under Networking and Resource Constraints

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Abstract—Motivated by the growing proliferation of federated learning (FL) in edge environments, we investigate the feasibility and performance of federated learning systems in real-world scenarios where networking and computing resources are highly constrained. This study introduces a virtual testbed specifically designed to recreate the harsh operational landscape in Africa, capturing the effects of resource-limited devices, network variability, and client failures. We reveal that practical FL frameworks, such as Flower, demonstrate remarkable adaptability across a wide range of network and client constraints, while exhibiting predictable breakdown points under harsher conditions. Through systematic investigation of connection patterns during FL training rounds, we demonstrate that periodic model update bursts separated by extended local training periods, create fundamental mismatches with standard TCP configurations. Our empirical evaluation identifies three transport parameters (`tcp_syn_retries`, `tcp_keepalive_time`, and `tcp_keepalive_intvl`), which handle connection management for sessions, and showed reduced training times under extreme network conditions. Building upon these insights, we propose a cross-layer optimization framework centered around an adaptive TCP Tuning Daemon design that would monitor connection state metrics to dynamically optimize transport parameters based on real-time network conditions. Our study contributes valuable insights demonstrating that cross-layer TCP optimization is essential for enhancing FL system tolerance and making federated learning more amenable for deployment in resource constrained settings.

Index Terms—federated learning, edge computing, distributed machine learning, network resilience

I. INTRODUCTION

Rapid advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) have led to an unprecedented demand for computational resources [1]. As AI/ML continues to evolve, the existing hardware struggles to keep up with the growing needs. This imbalance between demand and available computational power is most evident in Africa, where data centers and computing power are significantly more scarce than in Europe or the United States.

One way to mitigate the aforementioned resources challenges is to exploit the vast number of Internet of Things (IoT) devices that exist at the network edge. Individually, devices such as low-end smart phones, Raspberry Pis, and wireless sensor nodes, have limited potential, however their collective processing power can be substantial in bridging the gap between the computational demands of AI/ML and the available hardware. Moreover, the desire to train AI models on edge devices located in Africa naturally leads us to address its

unique challenges regarding connectivity and various types of outages.

As seen in Table I, which summarizes network latencies across continents [2], Africa experiences significantly higher latencies which in some instances go even beyond 400ms. These extreme conditions are not merely outliers but represent real scenarios faced in various African regions.

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF AVERAGE NETWORK LATENCIES ACROSS CONTINENTS
(ADAPTED FROM [2])

Continent	Average Latency (ms)
Africa	280
N. America	45
Europe	30
Asia	60
Australia	50

Furthermore, the higher rate of internet outages significantly reduces the availability of these devices, with numerous incidents reported across the continent. According to a study by CIPESA, governments in Africa have implemented internet shutdowns 59 times during protests, 25 times during elections, and 11 times during conflicts [3] [4].

In addition, the unreliable electricity supply in Africa poses a significant challenge given that these devices need a steady energy supply. Even when they are equipped with batteries or solar power, the frequent and often prolonged power outages across the continent make it nearly impossible to have them on and available for use all the time and accessible on a network [5]. In many African countries, power interruptions can last for hours or even days, far exceeding the capacity of most backup power solutions [5]. These disruptions impact network performance and contribute to the challenging internet landscape in Africa. Although these challenges are arguably more pronounced in Africa, similar constraints can very easily be experienced in many parts of the world, for example, due to request overload within a network.

This paper investigates the possibility of using Federated Learning (FL) [6] effectively and efficiently when leveraging edge devices that must operate under extreme conditions. Our main contributions are as follows:

- *Methodology for performance evaluation:* We designed and implemented a virtualized testbed for the rigorous evaluation of Federated Learning (FL) systems.

This testbed employs Kubernetes containers to emulate resource-constrained edge clients and integrates open-source chaos engineering tools, such as ChaosMesh, to systematically inject network faults, including variable latency and packet loss. This approach facilitates the reproducible analysis of FL performance and resilience under network conditions representative of challenging real-world deployments.

- *Characterization of FL resilience:* We conducted a systematic empirical study to define the operational boundaries of a prominent FL framework, Flower. By subjecting the system to progressively extreme network conditions, including network latencies up to 10 seconds and packet loss rates up to 50%, we demonstrate that while the framework exhibits initial robustness, its performance degrades substantially under sustained network stress. Our findings quantify the tipping points beyond which effective training becomes untenable.
- *Cross-layer optimizations:* Our investigation reveals that the observed performance degradation in FL is not solely an application-layer artifact but is fundamentally rooted in transport-layer inefficiencies. We demonstrate that synergistically tuning three critical TCP connection management parameters significantly accelerates model training under high-latency without compromising convergence quality.
- *Adaptive TCP Tuning Daemon:* Building upon our empirical findings, we propose the design of an adaptive connection management daemon that would monitor comprehensive connection state metrics to dynamically optimize transport parameters based on real-time network conditions.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II provides a background on Federated Learning and the motivation for its use in resource-constrained environments. Section III gives an overview of the related work. Section IV describes our experimental methodology, detailing our testbed along with experiments evaluating the effects of network constraints and client failure. Section V details our investigation into cross-layer optimization strategies. Section VI offers a discussion of our ongoing research efforts, and Section VII provides our concluding remarks.

II. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

As defined by McMahan et al. in "Communication-Efficient Learning of Deep Networks from Decentralized Data," Federated Learning is a machine learning technique that enables training models on distributed datasets across multiple devices or servers without exchanging the raw data. Instead of centralizing the data for training, FL allows each participating node to keep its data locally while collaboratively learning a shared model by exchanging only model updates [6]. Although its most common industry use is in maintaining data privacy, we use FL to obtain data parallelism that gives us the ability to aggregate several edge devices to train a model jointly while

achieving the same goal using a single edge device would be impossible or take a considerable amount of time.

We use Flower [7], an open-source end-to-end FL framework which distinguishes itself through its scalability, framework agnosticism, heterogeneity support, extensibility, and seamless transition. Flower’s architecture is built around a client-server model, where the server orchestrates the FL process and clients perform local computations on their respective datasets.

Flower’s architecture (Figure 1) comprises: (1) A Server: Manages the global model, coordinates training rounds, and aggregates model updates from clients using the federated averaging algorithm [8] to update the global model. A training round is a complete cycle of sending the global model to clients, performing local training, and aggregating the updated parameters on the server. (2) A set of Clients: Perform local training on their individual datasets and send model updates to the server. The framework’s core components include a ClientManager for handling client connections, a FL loop for coordinating the learning process, and a customizable Strategy abstraction for implementing specific FL algorithms [7].

Fig. 1. Architecture of the Flower Federated Learning Platform (Taken from Flower’s Documentation [7]).

Africa faces significant challenges with network performance and reliability, often due to underdeveloped infrastructure, frequent outages, and high latency. Several factors contribute to these issues:

- *Inadequate Infrastructure:* Although telecom companies installed their infrastructure such that the maximum latency and loss in remote areas are 300ms and loss 10% respectively [9], much of this infrastructure is ageing, resulting in inconsistent connectivity and bottlenecks during peak usage hours.
- *Power Supply Issues:* Electricity outages disrupt internet service providers and data centres, limiting consistent access to the internet [5].

- **Political Interference:** Governments in several African countries have implemented intentional internet blackouts during political unrest or elections, causing further disruptions [3] [4].
- **Limited Data Center Capacity:** Africa accounts for less than 1% of the world’s total data centre capacity, despite having around 18% of the global population [10].

These challenges manifest in poor network performance metrics across the continent, particularly in rural areas. Table II illustrates the stark contrast between network conditions in Africa and global averages. The disparity in data centre capacity further exacerbates these network issues. For context, South Africa, leading the continent with about 100 data centres, has only 200 MW of computing power, comparable to Switzerland, a much smaller country population-wise. This capacity shortage is projected to increase, with demand expected to exceed supply by 300% soon, driven by growth in cloud technologies, startups, mobile financial services, and AI deployment [10].

TABLE II
NETWORK METRICS: AFRICA (URBAN/RURAL) VS. GLOBAL AVERAGE

Metric	Africa		Global
	Urban	Rural	
Latency (ms)	100–300	500–3000	50–100
Packet Loss (%)	5–10	10–30	< 1
Internet Shutdowns	Frequent	Severe	Rare

In this study, we extend our experiments to test latencies as high as 10 seconds and packet loss up to 80% to evaluate FL performance under these challenging network conditions and discover where it breaks. By pushing the system to its breaking point, we can identify the specific failure modes, and lay the groundwork for developing robust optimization strategies that make FL truly practical for deployment in resource constrained environments.

Network Resilience: By default, Flower has no Google Remote Procedure Call (gRPC) maximum request retries and timeouts set which provides some resilience for poor networks. gRPC is a framework used to enable remote procedure calls between a server and clients. In addition, gRPC uses Transport Control Protocol (TCP) which provides message delivery guarantees through retries and acknowledgements which can be very useful in bad network conditions.

Client Resilience: Flower by default implements this by handling client disconnections gracefully and allowing clients to rejoin training after dropping out. It also provides an optional configuration feature to set request timeouts for the clients.

Note on Bandwidth Consideration: While bandwidth is an important metric in many network-dependent applications, we do not treat it as a primary concern in our study for several reasons. First, FL transmits only model updates instead of large datasets, reducing the data transfer load. For our use

case, with MNIST dataset, each client sends an average of 300 KB per model update.

Second, the communication in FL is periodic—occurring only at the end of each local training round—so continuous high-bandwidth usage is not required. Assuming 10 clients, the total data transfer per round is approximately 3 MB. If updates are transmitted over 10 seconds, the required bandwidth per client is about 0.24 Mbps, with an aggregate bandwidth of 2.4 Mbps for all clients.

Third, the asynchronous nature of FL allows clients to send updates independently, avoiding bandwidth bottlenecks that could arise with synchronous communication. Thus, our focus remains on latency, availability, and packet loss, which have a more significant impact on the performance of FL in resource-constrained environments.

III. RELATED WORK

The most closely related works [11], [12] explore the challenges associated with training and using AI models in resource-constrained environments, i.e., Africa. These works focus on understanding the challenges of specific AI-applications in specific countries. Our study tackles a broader problem by providing a fundamental analysis of the various network profiles that can be observed across various countries rather than those in very specific countries. In performing this broad analysis of the network profile space, our work identifies the specific set of network profiles where advanced reliability methods provided by complementary works [6] are required.

Many existing large-scale open source projects, e.g., TinyML, focus on optimizing AI inference within constrained devices. Our study explores an organizational problem, namely, training models on constraints devices in challenged networks. Related approaches on Federated learning on mobile devices, e.g., Alibaba’s Walle, generally focus devices which have richer device characteristics (e.g., smart phones) and these work often overlook the spectrum of network profiles that we examine.

Finally, there is a growing body of work on enhancing the model training aspect of federated learning to address a range of resource constraints from compute and network to client data and availability. These approaches provide a complementary solution to our recommendations. Similarly, work [13] that explores the feasibility and performance of federated learning on non-independent and identically distributed (non-IID) data, such as the image data that is prevalent in Africa, provide alternative designs to address the challenges that we highlight in our study.

IV. CHARACTERIZING FL RESILIENCE

In this section, we begin by providing a description of our experimental setup used for analysis, then we discuss our evaluation of Flower’s behavior under two network scenarios (*latency and packet loss*) and client failure. In each case, we provide an analysis of the results obtained and discuss the root cause of the observed behavior.

A. Experimental Setup

To rigorously evaluate FL performance and robustness, we designed and implemented a comprehensive experimental testbed. This section details the methodology and environment underpinning our experiments, including the configuration of the FL system, the mechanisms used to induce network and client variability, and the metrics employed for evaluation.

1) *Emulated Federated Learning Testbed:* We used the same experiment setup for all our analysis. We run the FL server and FL clients on two separate networks which were setup such that there was 0% packet loss and a latency of less than 5 ms to minimize noise in our results. Given the separate networks, we are able to instrument controlled network outages. As observed from our setup in Figure 2, clients run inside a containerized environment, i.e., Kubernetes cluster. In addition to simplifying management, Kubernetes enabled automated collection of key metrics (e.g., network traffic, CPU and RAM requests). In configuring the clients, our goal was to allocate resources which matched lowest specifications Raspberry Pi models, i.e., a 700 MHz ARM1176JZF-S processor (ARMv6 architecture) with 512 MB of RAM. To do this, we configured each client with 0.5vCPU.¹

Fig. 2. Federated learning test-bed

2) *Network Variability and Client Reliability:* To instrument network variability, we used Linux NetEm which provides control over network delays, packet loss, and bandwidth limitations². Our use of NetEM introduced network variability at server’s networking which enabled uniform control across the various clients. To instrument client failures, we used Chaos-Mesh, a tool for Kubernetes, which allows us to programmatically introduce container failures, and thus client failures.

3) *Evaluation Metrics:* In our experiments we focus on several key metrics:

¹ vCPU typically corresponds to one core running between 1 GHz and 1.4 GHz. Thus, allocating 0.5 vCPU provides a fair approximation of the Pi B’s 1-core running at 700 MHz[14]

²We fixed the limit (queue size) to 200

- **Accuracy:** We used the accuracy numbers reported by Flower which capture image prediction accuracy to evaluate the quality of the trained model.
- **Training time:** We calculated the training time as the time it took to complete a predefined number of rounds. We keep the number of rounds fixed across all experiments to ensure fairness and consistency.

B. Network and Client Resilience

We evaluate the resilience of flower under adverse network conditions and client failures. By simulating high latencies, significant packet loss, and frequent client dropouts, we can identify critical thresholds where performance degrades.

1) *Latency:* In Figure 3, we present the results from varying network latency. We observe that below 5000ms, the key impact of increased latency is to increase training time. This intuitively makes sense as network latency delays the time parameter updates reach the server.

Surprisingly, we observe that latency over 5000ms impacts both accuracy and training time. In fact, latency over 5000ms results in no training and thus zero accuracy. In analyzing the code base we observe that this is due to a set of timeouts at the transport layer (specifically Linux’s default TCP handshake timeout) which shuts down connections with significantly high latency. This is particularly problematic because Linux shuts down the connection at startup time and thus prevents anything communication and thus training.

Recommendation We found that this timeout can be easily fixed by configuring Linux’s default networking options, i.e., `/proc/sys/net/ipv4/`.

Fig. 3. Impact of latency

2) *Packet loss:* From Figure 4, we observe three key trends: First, low packet loss (e.g. below 30%) has no impact because the transport layer, i.e., TCP, contains mechanisms that retransmit packets and these mechanisms can effectively recover from packet loss.

Second, however, as packet loss increases from 30% to 50%, the model accuracy decreases by 0.3% and training time increases by 220%. We observe that given the magnitude of the loss, even the retransmitted packets are lost which significantly delays recovery.

Fig. 4. Impact of packet loss

Finally, we observe that loss over 50% results in the failure of Flower to train the model. Further analysis reveals that at such significantly high loss rates, the buffers used to store packets while waiting for the lost packets would run out of space.

Recommendation We found that the packet-loss induced model failure can be addressed by increasing the system’s buffer; however, we note that while such increase may prevent model failure, it will significantly impact model training times.

3) *Client Failure*: Figure 5 shows the impact of pod failure on FL model training time, and accuracy. We observe no significant impact in accuracy when less than 90% of the clients failed. Setting the minimum fit and evaluation set to 10% allows Flower to continue training the model when at least 10% of the clients are available thus tolerating 90% client failure rate. However, the training time did increase by 23% because it took longer to converge with fewer clients.

Recommendation We found that we can further increase Flower’s resilience to client failures by changing Flower’s minimum fit/evaluation configuration settings; specifically, lowering both of them.

Fig. 5. Impact of client failure rate

Table III provides a summary of our analysis and characterize regions of network performance and client outages where Flower performs Acceptable, Tolerable, and results in failure

of model training. We believe that such findings can be useful in helping operators and developers understand how Flower will behave in specific environments. As discussed perviously, the tolerable region can be extend by altering configuration of the systems or of Flower itself – these changes allow Flower to continue training during extreme conditions but generally at the cost of longer training times.

TABLE III
SUMMARY OF VIRTUAL ENVIRONMENT FAULT TEST RESULTS

Category	Acceptable	Tolerable	Failure
Network Delay (s)	< 0.3	5	> 5
Packet Loss (%)	< 10	30 - 40	> 50
Client Failure Rate (%)	< 50	50 - 70	> 90

V. CROSS-LAYER CONFIGURATION

The conventional wisdom in network protocol design often treats layers in isolation [15]. In this section, we explore the performance gains achievable through cross-layer configurations, specifically by tuning the TCP connection management parameters in `/proc/sys/net/ipv4/`.

A. TCP Network Parameters

As we established in our discussion on network resilience (II), Flower relies on TCP for the reliable delivery of messages. This dependency prompted us to explore the TCP parameters available in the network configuration directory. Our goal was to identify specific settings that could validate our hypothesis regarding the benefits of cross-layer optimization. Table IV lists the parameters we investigated, along with a brief description of the functionality each one controls [16]

TABLE IV
TCP MANAGEMENT PARAMETERS EXPLORED

TCP Parameter	Description
<code>tcp_syn_retries</code>	Prevents premature connection failure due to delayed SYN responses.
<code>tcp_synack_retries</code>	Ensures successful connection establishment despite delayed acknowledgments.
<code>tcp_keepalive_time</code>	Detects disruptions faster under high-latency conditions.
<code>tcp_keepalive_intvl</code>	Speeds up recovery from latency-induced issues.
<code>tcp_retries2</code>	Tolerates higher levels of packet loss before dropping connections.
<code>tcp_rmem/tcp_wmem</code>	Mitigates packet loss by increasing buffer sizes.
<code>tcp_max_syn_backlog</code>	Handles bursts of incoming connections caused by retransmissions.
<code>tcp_sack</code>	Reduces unnecessary retransmissions during packet loss.
<code>tcp_window_scaling</code>	Maintains larger windows for better throughput despite losses.

Based on these findings, we modified our experimental testbed to include scripts to help us explore unique values set

for each parameter. In each case, we tested ranges that span lower and upper bounds of the typically set default values.

B. Packet Loss

Our results showed minimal or no improvements to training time or accuracy for all tested parameters when compared with the default values set in each case. Figure 6 provides results for two exhaustive tests ran for `tcp_rmem/tcp_wmem` and `tcp_retries` respectively.

Fig. 6. Impact of `tcp_rmem/tcp_wmem` on packet loss

The minimal effect observed from tuning `tcp_rmem/tcp_wmem` parameters on training performance can be attributed to the distinct communication characteristics of FL workloads compared to traditional high-bandwidth network applications. These TCP parameters are designed primarily to optimize sustained data transfer scenarios with large payloads [17], where maximizing bandwidth utilization and handling packet loss in high-latency environments are critical. The periodic nature of FL communication, which occurs only at the end of each local training round, means that network optimization efforts are fundamentally misaligned with actual traffic patterns. Furthermore, the asynchronous communication model allows clients to send updates independently, eliminating bandwidth contention scenarios where TCP buffer optimizations would typically provide benefits.

C. Latency

While testing latency values within our TCP parameter space, we discovered three critical parameters that provided substantial improvements when compared to baseline performance of the default system values set. As observed in Figure 7, 8, and 9 our experiments with `tcp_syn_retries`, `tcp_keepalive_time`, and `tcp_keepalive_intvl` revealed significant performance gains under high-latency network conditions.

Figure 7 illustrates the critical impact of `tcp_syn_retries` on connection establishment in high-latency environments. Through our empirical analysis of the results 10 out of 17 latency data points (nearly 60% of the time), yielded suboptimal training performance. The data presented in Figure 8 repeats the same trend, alternative settings consistently outperform the default. Specifically, in 11 out of the 17 latency data points measured (approximately 65% of cases), the default `tcp_keepalive_time` resulted in longer training times compared

Fig. 7. The impact of `tcp_syn_retries` on latency

Fig. 8. The impact of `tcp_keepalive_time` on latency

Fig. 9. The impact of `tcp_keepalive_intvl` on latency

to other tuned values. Consequently, the same trend is shown in Figure 9, the default setting of 75 seconds consistently fails to deliver the best performance for FL workloads. Our analysis indicates that in 12 out of 17 latency scenarios (over 70% of our measurements), alternative `tcp_keepalive_intvl` values resulted in reduced training times. The default value creates a lengthy quiet period even after a connection is suspected to be

idle, delaying the detection of unresponsive clients. The strong correlation can be attributed to several key factors:

Connection Establishment Resilience (*tcp_syn_retries*):

Federated learning clients must establish reliable connections with the central server at the beginning of each training round. Under high-latency conditions (>100ms), the default *tcp_syn_retries* value of 5 often proves insufficient, leading to premature connection failures during the critical handshake phase.

Connection Maintenance (*tcp_keepalive_time/intvl*): The periodic nature of federated learning communication creates unique challenges for connection management. Unlike traditional web applications with continuous data streams, FL workloads exhibits bursty communication patterns during model update transmission, extended idle periods during local training phases, and sensitivity to connection drops that can invalidate entire training rounds.

D. Connection Management Daemon

From our empirical analysis demonstrates that the static, default configurations of TCP are ill-suited for the bursty communication patterns inherent in Federated Learning. This highlights a clear opportunity for dynamic, automated optimization. Building upon these insights, we propose an Adaptive TCP Tuning Daemon. This user-space daemon would operate by continuously monitoring real-time network state metrics, with a primary focus on Round-Trip Time (RTT) and connection establishment failures. Based on the observed conditions, it would dynamically reconfigure the key connection management parameters within the `/proc/sys/net/ipv4/` directory.

VI. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

The results presented in the previous sections uncover a fundamental mismatch between the transport protocol configurations used by Flower, and the unique demands of operating in constrained network environments. Our findings suggest that the challenges are not isolated to this framework alone. Since other prominent FL frameworks such as FATE and PySyft also rely on a gRPC-based network stack, the transport-layer inefficiencies we identified in Flower likely represent a systemic issue for the broader FL ecosystem. Building on these insights, our ongoing work is exploring several promising avenues to create more resilient and efficient FL systems:

- **Alternative Transport Protocols:** We are investigating modern transport protocols, particularly QUIC, as a promising alternative to TCP for FL workloads. Unlike TCP, QUIC's UDP foundation allows for more flexible congestion control algorithms better suited to high-latency, high-loss networks. Furthermore, features like reduced connection establishment overhead (zero-RTT) and resilience to connection migration could prove invaluable in environments with the kind of intermittent connectivity we have studied.
- **Comparative Analysis of FL Frameworks:** To understand if the observed transport-layer inefficiencies are

universal, we are extending our testbed to benchmark other popular FL frameworks. This comparative analysis will help determine whether our findings are specific to Flower's gRPC-based implementation or represent a more fundamental challenge for all FL systems relying on traditional network stacks.

- **Generalizing Across Diverse Datasets:** The efficacy of our proposed scheme has been demonstrated on the MNIST dataset. To guarantee its broader applicability, we are currently evaluating our cross-layer optimizations on a wider range of datasets, including more complex image data and other modalities.

VII. CONCLUSION

Deploying Federated Learning systems in resource-constrained environments such as those found in Africa, presents a significant challenge due to unreliable networks and limited client availability. In this paper, we presented an empirical study that moves beyond application-layer analysis to investigate the root causes of performance degradation at the network's transport layer. We designed and implemented a virtualized testbed to systematically characterize the resilience of Flower (a popular FL framework), identifying specific network latency and packet loss thresholds beyond which default configurations fail. Our core contribution is the demonstration that by synergistically tuning key TCP connection management parameters, it is possible to significantly reduce training time under extreme network conditions without compromising model accuracy. Building on these findings, we proposed the design of an adaptive daemon to automate this optimization. Ultimately, this work provides strong evidence that a cross-layer approach is not merely beneficial but essential for building robust FL systems capable of surviving the last mile at the network edge.

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